

Basic and Cognitive Emotions in Sound Perception

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Abstract

In the processing of sound two main stages can be discerned. In the first stage the sound is processed by the inner ear and certain perceptual attributes (loudness, roughness) result. In the second stage the sound is described and structured with knowledge present in long term memory. In emotion research a distinction is often made between basic emotions (e.g., pain, pleasure) and cognitive emotions (e.g., indignation, desire). In a theoretical framework it is hypothesized that the basic emotions are more related to the perceptual attributes that result from the sound processing by the inner ear, whereas the cognitive emotions are more related to the attributes that result from higher level processing in the brain. In a study, people had to rate emotion words (basic and cognitive) on a 10-point scale after hearing a sound. The sounds were everyday sounds and synthesized sounds. In addition to the rating the reaction time of a participant was measured. The latter measurement should enable us to make a distinction between the basic and the cognitive emotions. It was found that response times enabled a distinction between cognitive and basic emotions but not between different sounds. The analysis of the rating data revealed that cognitive and basic were mapped together. It is therefore suggested that in order to gain understanding in the underlying mental processes that result in certain emotions, response times are essential for our understanding and not the widely used rating scale data.

Keywords: product sound, emotion, cognition, process, response time

Introduction

The time that products could only be marketed using their qualitative and functional aspects seems to be far behind us. Nowadays, the emotional experience or emotional impact of a product becomes more and more important. It is therefore essential to investigate which emotions are relevant for industrial products and how people come to certain emotional judgments.

In the cognitive perspective of emotions, all emotions are the outcome of an appraisal process. An appraisal is a non-deliberate evaluation of the subjective relational meaning of a stimulus (see Arnold, 1960; Ortony, Clore, & Collins, 1988).

A distinction has been made between a complex process and a simple process of appraisal. The simple appraisals evoke emotions that are basic in the sense that these find their origin in

evolution. These basic emotions are needed for survival purposes and are often directly related to an action (e.g., Plutchik, 1980; Izard, 1977). For example, the emotion fear that is the outcome of an appraised 'physical threat' will result in the action to flee. Different researchers (e.g., Ekman, 1971; Izard, 1977; Plutchik, 1980; Tomkins, 1984) have indicated the same basic emotions and showed that these emotions exist in different cultures, in young children, and even in some animals. More complex, or evolved, appraisals evoke 'cognitive emotions' (see, Ortony, Clore, & Collins, 1988). An example of a cognitive emotion is inspiration, which requires an appraised 'mental illumination' (see Desmet, 2002).

In this study it is our aim to show that obtaining insight in these underlying processes is important in our understanding of the emotional experience of products. Five emotions have been chosen of which three are basic (happy, sad, active) and two are cognitive emotions (bored, inspired).

From our everyday practice, we know that people have different emotional experiences when they see the same products. Desmet (2003) has shown that these different experiences are not culture dependent but are more dependent on certain group characteristics. The question that needs to be solved is how do people come to these judgments. For this we need insight in the underlying mental processes. In most emotion research questionnaires have been used by which the emotional experience of people have been measured. The items reflecting emotions are often represented on the so-called circumplex of emotions (see, e.g., Russell, 1980; Mehrabian & Russell, 1977). However, cognitive and basic are often mapped together on this circle because they receive the same score on a scale. Consequently, no differentiation is obtained between cognitive and basic emotions and this distinction may be essential in our understanding how products evoke emotions. Desmet (this volume) showed that especially more subtle cognitive emotions are relevant for the emotional experience of industrial products. In addition, Van Egmond (2004) showed that the same cognitive emotions could also be used in capturing the emotional experience of frequency modulated sounds. These sounds are often used as alarm sounds and are related to psychoacoustical dimension of roughness (Zwicker & Fastl 1990: p.231-234). This means that low level processed perceptual features (like roughness) are somehow related to cognitive emotions. The focus of this study is on the emotional experience of product sounds.

Sound becomes more and more important in the design of industrial products. It is well-known that products are often returned to the manufacturers if they make the wrong sounds. Because people need auditory feedback one cannot design only silent products. In addition, sound plays a role in the emotional experience of industrial products. For example, the gurgling of a drip filter coffeemaker is an essential part of our experience in making coffee. The sound of a product should be designed in such a way that it evokes a certain experiential quality that fits the design concept or certain brand values of a company. However, research lacks that investigates the experiential experience of product sounds. Van Egmond & Van Balken (in progress, 2004) have showed that the sounds of a coffeemaker could be improved by redesigning the sound on the basis of perceptual attributes. There is some literature available that describes the experience of sounds that have similar properties (noisy) as product sounds (e.g., Von Bismarck, 1974; Västfjäll, Gulbol, Kleiner, & Gärling, 2002). However, none of this research investigates the actual process that leads to a certain emotional experience. Sound is especially interesting to use in this research because several stages can be identified in the processing of sound. Aspects that result from bottom-up processing (e.g., psychoacoustical measures loudness, roughness) and aspects that result from top-down processing (e.g., identification, attributes like penetrating, heavy) can be identified. We suggest that aspects resulting from bottom-up processing might relate more to basic emotions, whereas aspects that result from top-down processing might relate to more cognitive emotions. However, before these hypotheses can be tested it is necessary to investigate if response times can be a means to identify basic and cognitive emotions.

In this study we will try to investigate to what extent product sounds relate to basic and cognitive emotions. In addition, response times will be collected in order to investigate if it is possible to make a distinction between basic and cognitive emotions. The used sounds will be existing sounds that have a certain ecological validity and completely new synthesized sounds.

Method

People were asked to rate as fast as possible 8 sounds on 5 emotions using a 10-point scale.

Participants

Fifty-four students (25 male and 29 women) of the Delft University of Technology participated in this study. They were between 18 and 25 years of age. The students reported normal hearing and volunteered.

Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli were existing sounds (ecological valid) and synthesized sounds. The sounds were between 1 and 2 seconds in duration. The sounds are presented in Table 1. In the first column of this table the name of a sound is presented and in the second column the description of a sound is given.

<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>
Bell	A metal bell sound
Cork	Popping of a cork from a bottle
Click	Short click sound
FMPleas	Frequency modulated sound with a low roughness level and onset and offset envelopes
FMUnPleas	Frequency modulated sound with a high roughness level and without onset and offset envelopes
Guitar	Struck string of a guitar
Noise	the sound of white noise
Sin7600	A sine wave of 7600 Hz, sounds like glass

Table 1, Description of Stimulus Material

Five emotions were selected: three basic emotions (happy, sad, active); two cognitive emotions (bored, inspired). Stimulus presentation and data collection were done with a specially written program in MAX/MSP 4.2 (Cycling 47). A slider (see Figure 1) consisting of a linear potentiometer fixed onto a wooden plate was used to collect the response data. The plate made an angle of approximately 30 degrees with the table on which it was placed. Next to the slider a scale from 1 through 10 was indicated on the wooden plate (not presented in the figure). The slider was hooked up via an I-Cube to the USB-port an Apple Macintosh computer. The I-Cube read out the slider every 10ms. The emotion words were presented on top of the slider with cards.

Figure 1, The slider employed to collect rating data and response times.

Procedure

The participant was seated in front of the slider. It was explained that (s)he had to rate 8 sound stimuli on 5 different emotions using a 10 point scale. Thus, each participant received 40 trials. The number 1 indicated that the emotion was not evoked to a high extent and the number 10 indicated was evoked to a high extent. The participant was asked to make the judgment as fast as possible after (s)he heard the sound. The response time was recorded when the subject started to move the slider. The emotions were presented as words on cards that could easily be exchanged on top of the slider by the experimenter. The emotion words were presented in a fixed order over the participants (inspired-bored-active-happy-sad). The sounds were presented in a random order for each participant. Before each experimental trial started the participant received one training trial with a different sound than in the experimental trials.

Results

Due to technical difficulties approximately 1.5% of the data were missing (randomly distributed over participants and experimental conditions). The missing values were replaced by the mean of an experimental condition (the combination of 1 level of the factor sound and 1 level of the factor emotion). The replacement was necessary in order to be able to perform a repeated measure analysis.

Response time

In Figure 2 the mean response time and the standard error are presented as a function of Emotion (figure A) and as a function of Sound (figure B). It can readily be seen that there is an effect of emotion on the mean response times (Figure 2A). The emotion “happy” clearly has the fastest mean response time. The emotions “sad” and “active” have approximately the same mean response times (slower than “happy”). The emotions “inspired” and “bored” also have approximately the same mean response times (slower than “happy”, “sad”, and “active”). No clear effect of Sound on the mean response times can be seen in Figure 2B.

Figure 2, In figure A the response time as function of Emotion (5 levels) has been represented. In figure B the response time as a function of Sound (8 levels) has been presented. The error bars indicate the standard error of the mean.

The response time data were analyzed using a repeated measures analysis (general linear model). All tests were conducted using a α -level of .05. The analysis revealed only a significant effect of Emotion on response times, $F(4,50)=35.71, p<.0001$. No significant effect for Sound and for the interaction effect between Emotion and Sound were found, $F(7,47)=.97, p=.47$ and $F(28,26)=.66, p<.05$, respectively.

Rating data analysis

In Figure 2 the mean rating scale values as a function of Emotion and of Sound (indicated by separate lines) are shown. The standard error bars have not been added to enhance readability. It can be seen that the participants have used the complete range of the rating

scale. Especially for emotion “happy” the mean rating values differ for the different sounds. The sounds “Noise” and “FMUnPleas” have a very low mean rating value on the scale of happy, whereas the “FMPLeas”, the “Bell”, and the “Sin7600” (sounds as glass) sounds have relatively high mean rating values. As can be expected the mean rating values flip over for the opposite emotion of “happy”, that is, “sad”. A sound with high “happy rating” obtains a low “sad rating”. However, it can be seen that the participants used a smaller range of the rating scale for the emotion “sad” than for the emotion “happy”. “Noise”, “Cork”, and “FmUnPleas” are sounds that are constant over time and they receive the lowest mean “Active” ratings. The other sounds have amplitude envelopes that change over time and receive higher mean “active” ratings. The mean ratings for the emotions “Inspired” and “Bored” to the different sounds show similar effects as for the emotions “Happy” and “Sad”, respectively.

Figure 2, The mean rating scale values as a function of Emotion (5 levels) and of Sound (8 levels). The sounds have been indicated by different markers. In the legend the sounds and their corresponding markers have been depicted. The lines between the markers have been added to improve readability only.

The mean rating values for the emotions were: Active, 5.21; Bored, 5.12; Happy, 5.13; Inspired, 5.06; Sad, 4.69. The mean rating values for the sounds were: Bell, 5.17; click, 5.60; Cork, 4.77; FMPLeas, 5.60; FMUnPleas, 4.36; Guitar, 5.35; Noise, 4.12; Sin7600, 5.42. A repeated measure analysis (using Wilk’s lambda) was performed on the rating scale data with

Emotion and Sound as within-factors. All tests were conducted using an α -level of .05. A significant effect of Sound was found, $F(7, 47)=12.07, p<.0001$. The effect of Emotion almost reached significance, $F(4,50)=2.47, p=.06$. The interaction effect was also significant, $F(28,26)=18.24, p<.0001$.

An hierarchical cluster analysis using Ward's method was performed on the mean rating scale data. The analysis revealed two main clusters "Happy" and "Inspired" on the one hand, and "Active", "Bored", and "Sad" on the other.

Discussion

Our main finding is that a differentiation can be made on the basis of response times between emotions that theoretically should stem from a complex appraisal process and emotions that theoretically should stem from a simple appraisal process. The effect is in the expected direction, i.e., more complex emotions give rise to higher response times than more basic emotions. The response times did not differ for the sounds. This indicates that the "perceptual" processing of the different sound events were approximately the same. There was also no difference in response times between the more "ecological" valid sounds and the synthesized sounds. These findings combined with the lack of an interaction effect clearly show that the difference in response times can only result from the difference in the processing of the emotion words and is not an effect of sound. Because response times are a measure to identify the complexity of a mental process, our findings support the view that the underlying appraisal process is an important aspect in the differentiation between emotions.

The rating scale values differ over sounds and emotions. This general finding indicates that people understood the task they were asked to do. The mean rating values over the emotions do not differ. This is expected because otherwise a response bias would be present for one emotion over the other. In other words, this would mean that one emotion would always be rated higher or lower than another emotion. The significant difference between the sounds indicate that people judged certain sounds always lower than the other sounds. However, it should be noticed that the range of the mean rating values is rather small (4.12 through 5.60) compared to the range of the scale (1 through 10). The interaction effect is understandable because of the opposite ratings for the emotions for certain sounds.

Our findings also suggest that the use of rating scales do not allow a distinction between emotions that should be treated different on the basis of the underlying mental processes. This statement is supported by combining the response time findings with the rating scale findings. Inspired and Happy are in the same cluster on the basis of the rating scales. In addition, Bored and Sad are also clustered together. Consequently, on the basis of rating scales these emotions are grouped together. However, on the basis of response times Inspired and Bored are grouped together, and Happy and Sad are grouped together. This means that dependent on the type of theoretical question one is asking one should use response times or rating scale data or both.

It is shown that response times can be efficiently used to group emotions on the basis of the underlying mental processes. This study used only a limited number of emotions and sounds that were based on a selection criterion, “ecological valid” versus synthesized sounds. In this study, perceptual aspects of and descriptive features of sounds that result from bottom-up and top-down processes have not been systematically manipulated. It is our aim in future research to systematically manipulate these different aspects resulting from these different processes and investigate the effect on the response times in the judgment of basic and of complex emotions.

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